

**PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES OF ALIKHONTORA SOGUNI IN
DEVELOPING THE MORAL QUALITIES OF TEENAGE STUDENTS**

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Annotation: In this article, the pedagogical views of Alikhontora Soguni on the development of moral qualities of adolescent students are described, as well as relevant conclusions are drawn on this topic.

Key words: morality, moral qualities, education, training, knowledge, youth, teenager, student, perfection, Alikhantora Soguny , spirituality, spiritual heritage.

In life so category people will be because they are their lives during did works periods relevance even if it passes does not lose and incomparable importance occupation is enough Such people name to eternity it is good . The words of our prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). with note as mentioned , " people the good ones are better than the angels . ¹Some good intending and pure hearty people people between snobbery with humble living pass they go However , it is known time after their how much great and dear that they are homeland and compatriots for for How It's sad , my dear intention and the nation for even staring at death , own his life how many times danger and to danger that they put understand starts . They left gone spiritual wealth own to the people forever heritage being How much is left ? generation from this enjoy will be

That's it tenacious , own his soul people and nationality sacrificed for great from people one Alikhontora Shakirkhantora son Soguni . Former USSR state during Alikhanto'ra Soguny about almost never how official information unspeakable , this a person about different -district, often to each other opposite sentence- words walks was People between this appreciative adjectives with one in line some ok who are by said false rumors walked

" History about paper is small when condemned science manners according to one mouth excess not to say a word or not reduce " obligation " ²he said was

¹ How was Alikhontora Soguni kidnapped? | Khurshid Davron Library (kh-davron.uz)

² From Uvaishkhontora Shakirov's article "About my great grandfather and the work "The Sorrow of Turkistan". [www . ziya , en](http://www.ziya.en) from the library .

Alikhontora Soguni . That's why for , I mean great a person , a great enlightener and political of the character vital activity about word when walking this including programming as to use I thought it was better . Because this is sentence himself Alikhontora Soguni's How fair and truthful of being bright is proof .

Perfection is human perfection level expressive spiritual from concepts become his to himself special criteria there is will be Ignorant relatively wise , careless relatively watchful , miserly relatively generous , lazy relatively brave , cowardly relatively bravery such as traits perfection for to himself special measure tool be service does Human perfect person be in maturity physical and spiritual beauty incomparable place occupies Both physically and mentally healthy to be not only personal , perhaps , the same at rest social value is also counted . Of perfection again one to himself special criterion this to the country , to the nation loyalty with service is to do O'z Homeland did not love , nationality history and fate relatively indifferent in the spirit looking after of a person perfection about while never how the word to be possible it's not .

Our great grandfather Alikhontora Not only Soguni wise , alert , generous , active , brave , and also sincerely devoted to the Motherland loving , own nationality destiny about who cares perfect a person to be , own of the time many sciences perfect occupied great from all was Alikhantora Soguni religious science and theology in the field big to knowledge have that it was and popularity present in the day to many it is known . In particular , his " History Muhammadi 's work from the publication from the exit then that person only in our country not but whole islam became famous in the world . With that together , it is high intelligence owner , history of science , especially Islam history and Turkestan of history wise from scholars was

Tests under past of life last 30 years during Alikhontora Soguni to the pen belongs to huge spiritual heritage inside his " Turkestan grief " is historical Poem incomparable place occupies In this work his faith , outlook , how goals for that he fought , the people of the Motherland to what motivation , another to the state of addiction reasons and him national to independence take exit ways in particular his opinions , the independence of the Motherland strengthening for what are to do necessary the fact that issue deep meaningful thoughts own expression found and statement done Including his himself this of his work word at the beginning him from writing purpose as follows statement says : "Now, my country me don't sleep as long as I have it because of my love , my share me don't know as long as I have it from what I know , on the Motherland happening historical changes and that too future good or bad the results showing the children of the Motherland as an example , etc from this lesson as it is historical one work to write i entered However , I am

alone pro-Islam it's not I was , maybe as soon as I was injured humanitarian I was To the people which road goodness do it that I won't get it , youth my periods grief days with I spent And now my hair and beard I am pale and old enough My age to Saxon achieved , internal-external my strength back retirement , old age load under curl up standing in front of us look started destruction pit that it is approaching I can't stand it , the future joint our descendants care for , har don't side difficulties anyway , that's it history to write I started My pen from the language pain my words bloody the eye I'm young join this book sheets to the face spilled was That's why for of this name " Turkistan" . " I put " ³sadness .

In the book, in addition to thoroughly studying modern science, mastering the knowledge of modern techniques and technology, raising the national pride and national consciousness of the people, preserving our mother tongue, and promoting literature is our nation's duty. it is stated that it is a force that protects from being swallowed up: "If our current children of the Motherland are educated and understood, if they do not have a national feeling, it will never be possible for them to benefit us, that is, their people. Maybe ax stalk from ourselves as it was released , yov in the hands of our roots with cut to dry weapon will be In that case while from themselves hope done homeland of his sons hands with homeland people to bury deep is dug up so National from our authority for now break up standing even though it is national from our feelings without separating him save if we can , in the future to enemies from swallowing ourselves save we can Now this to the goal reach for placed of issues the most the first condition language is the issue . If we language our literature expanding his value increase and other cultural languages level enough here we are when our nation , national our emotions constant respectively grow up is to save . If so maybe , on the contrary , own mother language to the value without enough to him importance don't give they are , at that time a lot not far away goodbye say , own from their languages forever divorced will be So be own mother from the language separation , national feelings loss is the result . This is work while humanity world in front great betrayal , unforgivable crime is considered It happened like this that is , the great Turkestan great Turan offspring invaders wishful , victim has been without to the crisis God bless you save it , history on the pages glory badges of honor will be deleted that means " ⁴. This of thoughts We will prove it to Alikhon It is called " About Language " by Soghuni from the poem given the following we also find in the passage can :

"If he despises person own language ,

³ Alikhanto'ra Soguni . " Turkistan sadness " . - T.: " Sharq " publishing house , 2003 . - 10 pages.

⁴ Alikhanto'ra Soguni . " Turkistan sadness " . - T.: " Sharq " publishing house , 2003 . - 22 pages.

A traitor to the country , an enemy of the country .

When breastfeeding entered mother language erur

Mother father the right , save it ⁵. "

Indeed , language national unity provider from vostas one which one is listed the nation own mother to his tongue betrayal If it does , it is his own To the country , to the nation is betrayal . After all, language the nation of spirituality is a mirror .

The work is amazing clear , artistic beautiful room , clear in the language written Including nature of the scenery images of students in the heart mother Homeland relatively deep love and love feeling wakes up . "...This is historic the words from writing intended my ultimate goal , he says Alikhantora , own In his homeland standing up a stranger has been Turkestan people , especially today and the future youth of the Motherland warning , death from sleep is to wake up . In my mind mungy my sorrows pencil from the beak pour out wrote this my book student and also the hearer patriot , nationalist hero to our children my my assignment that's my language from the tip not pain my language from within out wrote warmth my words only just listen without passing every one mouth the word checking his on thought let them walk . Humanity development not culture development in the 20th century people national , native , religious rights storage for which things to the hand to bring necessary that good understand , his measure let them enter . ⁶A person national independence for inviter this words in the heart infinite pride of feeling to wake up , national unity of feeling strong root to shoot cause will be

of these words practical expression as , Alikhontora Soguni already in 1962 great host Our ancestor Amir Temur's " Tuzuklari Temur " . the book old persian from the language Uzbek to the language translation does of this book many p part first of all " Guliston " magazine on the page in 1967 of that person courageous access the word with clicked comes out That's it during the " bloodthirsty " period Temur". justified to write big courage and requires patience was However , our grandfather owner Amir Temurni Uzbek to the people by resurrecting giving gone were From this one year then , that is , in 1968 Uzbekistan Sciences of the academy vice president IMMo'minov "Amir Temurin in the history of Central Asia held place and role " in the pamphlet caution with that person tries to give a positive assessment . From this after Uzbekistan in the press almost 25 years during this in the subject information not given In 1991, "Temur 's rule " again book was published in the form

⁵ Alikhontora Soguni . Poems | Khurshid Davron Library (kh-davron.uz)

⁶ Alikhanto'ra Soguni . " Turkistan sadness " . - T.: " Sharq " publishing house , 2003 . - 25 pages.

Also, Alikhontora Soguny a person own purpose on the way persistence with to stand Therefore, if a believer is a Muslim one unfair work if he sees, of course, ul to work hand with against standing if it is necessary power if not enough, the language with if he ca n't return it, he wo n't if not happy with dissatisfied to be, however a person happy ul to work dissatisfied that it was if he doesn't notice, that's it case faithless of people sign that, such category " people". our prophet are alive that they said he was dead note is enough

He is every always the people knowledge to get invitation reached Therefore, " Rights of protection the most we are strong weapon calculated science, education doors present in the day a person world to the face Entirely is open. For this reason Our fathers and daughters who understand modern every science basis with good understand the opportunity as long as knowing to master from others more introductions " It is necessary, " 7he said was In particular, it is called " Uygon ". in his poem everyone science to get, knowledge didn't happen in the place while pride and independence not to be hint that 's it says :

" My existence save if you say, science you did do it good,
No while go ahead don't do anything never who question
The surface of the earth changed, but you changed we have no,
Cindy Turkestan of the world At the beginning of face a thousand stick " 8.

That's it period said this thoughts today's more and more globalizing, spiritual threats getting stronger going high technologies in the time his own the proof complete confidence that he is finding with say i can Because today in the day achieved of achievements all a person of knowledge is the result.

Alikhanto'ra scientific and literary of activity a lot yearly difficult work product " History Muhammadi 's work is considered This is it of the work writing the future generation internal the world of impoverishment prevention get, forever values the price our prophet Muhammad Mustafa, peace be upon him alayhi vassal histories with introduction through save to stay on the way done great is jihad. Alikhanto'ra his own whole content this is his life good to work in the gift did science the owner was

Alikhanto'ra really encyclopedist, broad knowledge the owner was His above to the language received from his works except to medicine about " Healing ul - ilal ", that is, " Illats " healing " is also available. This is it in the book two from the face many p different different diseases statement, diagnosis and treatment methods cause passed. Alikhanto'ra strong I was also a doctor, east treatment protect to stay

⁷ Alikhontora Soghuniy. "Sadness of Turkestan". - T.: "Sharq" publishing house, 2003. - 176 pages.

⁸ [Alikhontora Soguni. Poems | Khurshid Davron Library \(kh-davron.uz\)](#)

on the way did good works , efforts is productive . In this regard series medicine also mentoring his professors did of the judge point of view view - "There is one disease , one cure hundred " and " Whole the mountain is a stone, the earth is blue - like a pharmacy was Procedure food , diet , food to eat norm and of mechkai damage about many p would say

Many p languages deep that he knew so , that's it in languages they also wrote poems . He is also the owner of the "Devoni Sog' uniy " office is also His office the fundamental basis of its content homeland , nation love , his independence preserve with dependent fireworks calls organize is enough In this Devonian , especially , " **Homeland and science or seven Star** " , " **Where are you ?** " , " **About language** " , " **Wake up** " , " **Drops** " , " **Stay alone** " , " **Historical Monument** " , " **Prepare** " . **poems national unity in understanding separately important have Including below his " Homeland and science or seven from the poem " star** " . given four while this my opinion obvious is an affirmation :

" The homeland friend catch of faith ermish ,
That's why right Rasuldin saying to be
Motherland those who do not love of us do n't
Who is this ? if he doesn't know to faith do not enter .⁹

From this besides , Alikhanto'ra Soguny by and Ahmad Donish's " Navodir" . ul-waqae " work , Darvesh Ali Changi's " Music treatise " work , Mojoy Orientalist Herman Julius of Vambery valuable Poem " Movarounnahr " . or Bukhara history " work while Ottoman Turk from the language Uzbekized and this translations today's history today science take over about important from sources one being service is doing

Summary instead of that's it note reach maybe we are young generation Hazrat Imam al- Bukhari to the offspring our belonging with We respect you , from Temur's generation that we are with We are proud , Alikhantora Soguny our countryman that it was with we are proud . That's it great figures that's it From the homeland that it came out for , they universal values the founders and preachers that they were for and so are we the nation from the people that we are for this Motherland we love It is national culture , religion, morality of their beauty complex that it was for , identity understanding pride in hearts wake up for even more we love Young generation that's it holy To our homeland , to our great ancestors worthy being thought behavior , labor act and never from whom less not to be the goal by doing to the future desire need ! Then our great grandfathers happy souls and the future of the country calm down will be

⁹ [Alikhontora Soguni . Poems | Khurshid Davron Library \(kh-davron.uz\)](https://www.kh-davron.uz)

LIST OF REFERENCES :

1. Alikhanto'ra Soguni . " Turkistan sadness " . - T.: " Sharq " publishing house , 2003 .
2. How was Alikhontora Soguni kidnapped? | Khurshid Davron Library (kh-davron.uz)
3. Alikhontora Soghuniy. Poems | Khurshid Davran Library (kh davron.uz)
4. From Uvaishkhontora Shakirov's article "About my great grandfather and the work "The Sorrow of Turkistan". www.ziyo.uz from the library .
5. Tursunboyevich AO Development of socially active citizenship competence in students and youth in continuous education. - 2022.
6. Tursunboyevich OA Pedagogical and psychological opportunities for the development of socially active civic competences in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – No. 3. - S. 1888-1897.
7. Abduganiyev O. Formation of legal training aimed at competitiveness in pupils of secondary schools //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2019. – T. 9. – No. 7.
8. Tursunboyevich OA Pedagogical and psychological opportunities for the development of socially active civic competences in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – No. 3. - S. 1888-1897.
9. Abduganiyev OT FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS //E Conference Zone. - 2022. - S. 10-13.
10. Oglu AOT Pedagogical Conditions And Mechanisms Of Development Of Socially Active Civil Competence In Students //Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education. – 2021. – T. 12. – No. 7. – S. 433-442.
11. Abdug Aniyev O. DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCE OF GENERAL HUMAN VALUES IN STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A CULTURAL STUDY APPROACH //Science and innovation . - 2023. - T. 2. - no. Special Issue 9. – P. 316-319.
12. O'G Abdug'Aniev Free Tursunboy . "PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF DEVELOPING SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS." Science and innovation 2. Special Issue 5 (2023): 708-713.
13. Tursunboyevich , Abduganiyev Free . "Development of socially active citizenship competence in students and youth in continuous education." (2022).